

DESIGNING AN APPROACH FOR IMPROVING COMMUNICATION ABILITY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL PUPILS

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Abstract. this article discusses about creating an approach for developing communication ability of secondary school pupils. Furthermore, it provides some feasible suggestions from the point view of pedagogs.

Keywords: *communicative approach, speech, grammar, principle.*

The communicative approach has been at the forefront of schoolchildren's speech development methods for the past few years. Potential communication with other members of the community is involved, and communication is intended to persuade others to agree with one's point of view while also providing information. Based on the study of linguistic units as text-forming ones engaged in speech generation and formulation, the communicative method was developed. The syntactic structure is viewed in the context of this orientation as a functional unit with a specific range of application. In terms of speech development, the communicative method is linked to how kids learn language norms in all kinds of speech activities - receptive, productive, oral, and written - while taking the communication environment into consideration. In the words of T.M. Voitelova, "such training promotes a conscious attitude to the language system, its norms and categories, and the rules for choosing the right language unit, it allows you to work most effectively on all types of speech activity in accordance with the age stages of speech development and the leading activity of students - this is the way from speech activity to comprehension and analysis of language units necessary for solving communicative, cognitive and educational tasks, in the unity of their meaning, form and function" [1].

Within the context of the communicative orientation, researchers like E.V. Arkhipova, A.P. Eremeeva, G.G. Gorodilova, V.I. Kapinos, L.P. Fedorenko, T.A. Ladyzhenskaya, and M.R. Lvov examined the circumstances and phases of how students' speech activity forms. These authors suggest using a systemic and complete approach to the study of speech development, integrating students' linguistic theory studies with practical communicative activities under particular communication scenarios.

This definition of student speech development methodology as a subset of student language methodology is widely accepted. It studies "methods and techniques for enriching and activating the vocabulary of students, forming the grammatical structure of student speech (morphological means, phrases, sentences), coherent speech - monologue and dialogue, narration, description studies the levels of speech proficiency at different levels of learning and typical speech errors, their frequency, causes and ways of elimination" [2]. Such a viewpoint is consistent with the communicative orientation as, within the parameters of the speech development approach, all linguistic levels and speech patterns are taken into consideration, including oral and written speech acts. Its goal is to get pupils ready for successful verbal communication. The primary goals are to pinpoint the root causes of speech mistakes and provide practical solutions for their eradication (via training exercises and activities).

At the moment, the following departments differ in their approaches to teaching the English language: vocabulary development, sentence construction, composition, and enhancing students' speech patterns. [2]. Through the enhancement of students' communicative capacity, we comprehend "the process of mastering speech: the mechanisms of speech - its perception and expression of one's thoughts" and "the means of language (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar, speech culture, styles)" [2]. According to M.R. Lvov, mastering the culture of speech, the development of speech's physiological mechanisms, the need for communication, the ability to express one's thoughts, the existence of a speech environment that provides linguistic nourishment for a child's speech development, and the presence of meaningful material that forms speech's content are the primary requirements for a child's successful development of speech [2]. It is important to remember that environmental factors can have both beneficial and bad effects, such as causing speech problems, improper wording, etc. Given the impact of society, educators ought to act as cultural norm interpreters and practice modeling good speech in the classroom.

Thus, one of the four main pillars of the general approach to learning English is the development of pupils' speech. In addition to being able to comprehend and analyze the writing of others, students should be able to conduct dialogues and express

themselves both orally and in writing in a way that is appropriate for the communication environment and the statement's goal [3].

According to T.M. Voiteleva, who bases her technique on L.P. Fedorenko, the following are the fundamentals of speech development methodology: the principle of unity of speech and thinking development (a child's speech development is closely related to the development of certain mental operations: synthesis, analysis, abstraction, generalization, induction, and deduction); the principle of language learning and speech learning (units of language are assimilated in the unity of their knowledge - the principle of reliance on the syntactic model); the principle of communicative development (promotes full-fledged communication both orally and in writing); the contextual principle, which analyzes linguistic units in the context of their relationships, and the continuity of work on speech development, which involves frequent speech development exercises in classes as part of learning English [1].

As we can see, there is ongoing integration taking place in the area of schoolchildren's speech development. These guidelines are predicated on the idea that speech is an activity in which students are the subject. Therefore, developed thinking (schoolchildren need to work on developing their inner speech), imagination, and creativity, as well as awareness of the rules of language (literary standard) and the environment in which communication occurs, are prerequisites for effective communication. In addition, the author themselves should view the text as a single cohesive unit with a clear composition (introduction, main part with thesis and arguments, and conclusions), understanding of the goals and objectives that must be carried out, rather than as something fragmented, fragmentary, and situational (which is often the result of young people's "clip thinking"). As a result, the verbal utterance takes on a social orientation, intended to communicate the speaker's objectives and viewpoint to the listener.

It would also be hard to ignore the ethical aspect of the problem. As part of the process of helping students develop their communicative competence, teachers should also focus on helping students convince others of their rightness through verbal rather than physical means, respect for the opposing party and their viewpoint, reflection on what others have said, and the capacity to agree or rationally disagree. These guidelines align with the findings of M.R. Lvov, who takes into account the

physiological mechanisms of speech development, the need for communication, the expression of ideas, the existence of a speech environment that supports a student's developing speech, the presence of significant material that contributes to speech content, mastering theoretical knowledge of language, its patterns, correcting speech constantly, adhering to its studied rules, and mastering the culture of speech [2].

List of used literature

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